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Thinking the Unthinkable: Cyber Attacks on India's Nuclear Assets

Abstract

The high reliance of nuclear weapons on computers has outstretched the susceptibilities of the cyber war against them. While other countries are not discounting the cyber threat against its nuclear weapons, India has officially maintained the position that the present systems and technologies that it is employing, ensures safe handling of its nuclear assets against all cyber-attacks. However, there are certain loopholes in the present C2 structures, which need to be examined and addressed. The cyber threats against the nuclear C2 structures can cause delay in India's response time, in a situation of retaliation. In such a scenario, it would be difficult to absorb the extent of the first strike of the enemy, and the cyber warfare may result in a catastrophic impact on the communication systems. A cyber-attack can also be the cause for technical failures in the civil nuclear program, which may lead to uncontrolled leakage of radiation. This article explores various possibilities of cyber warfare against India's nuclear weapon systems, which can be a serious threat to its critical infrastructure.

Keywords: Nuclear Weapons, Nuclear Security, Cyber war, India, Command and Control Structure, Retaliation

Introduction

Nuclear weapons were developed in 1945 and though they were not immune to cyber threats then, there was an absence of any challenge from the cyber

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domain. However, the integration of the *nuclear command and control* (C&C) structures with computers has given rise to the dependability of nuclear weapons on cyber tools (Gartze and Lindsay 2017, 37) and has raised a new threat perspective that cyber-attacks and warfare can be conducted against nuclear assets as well. The *International Atomic Energy Agency* (IAEA) has acknowledged the seriousness of cyber threats to nuclear weapons. In June 2015, the IAEA hosted an international conference on “Computer Security in a Nuclear World” in Vienna. The IAEA Director General, Yukiya Amano called for an international response to tackle the global threat posed by criminals and terrorists bent on launching cyber-attacks against nuclear facilities. (Donovan 2015) He emphasized on the importance of strengthening computer security capabilities at the State and facility level, to guard against cyber threats that could adversely affect nuclear security. It is an absolute necessity to ensure fool-proof cyber security of the nuclear assets since potential cyber threats could have a security impact upon the nuclear security systems and may damage it. The Director General mentioned:

Strengthening computer security capabilities at the State and facility level, to guard against cyber threats that could adversely affect nuclear security, remains a high priority for the Agency and for Member States. (Director General Statement at High Level Dialogue on Nuclear Security 2017).

Computer security constitutes an important aspect of nuclear security with the newly expanding application of digital systems. With increasing digitalization, India has gradually emerged as a significant target from the cyber security point of view. Digitalization has led to heavy reliance on digital instrumentation or digital control systems or computer based information systems (IS). Further, the dependability of nuclear weapons on C&C structures, which are linked to computers, gives rise to the possibility of a cyber intrusion against them. This development has augmented the threat of compromising nuclear C&C structures.

Recently, several government departments in India have faced repeated cyber-attacks. These departments include the Prime Minister’s Office (PMO), the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA), the Indo-Tibetan Border Police Force, the Defence Research and Development Organization (DRDO) and many other Indian websites (India is quietly preparing a cyber-war unit to fight this new enemy from 2018). According to the 2018 Internet Security Threat Report, “India has emerged as the third most vulnerable country to cyber threats, such as malware, spam and ransom ware, in 2017.” (Bhargava 2018).

With a burgeoning population, increasing internet literacy, expanding critical infrastructure and a rapidly developing economy, India has become vulnerable to cyber terrorism and cyber espionage. As a state with advanced nuclear capability, India is vigilant towards potential cyber threats to its nuclear weapons system. Despite this, there is a huge gap in India's capability and capacity to safeguard against a potential cyber intrusion. The rising magnitude of cyber threats makes it important to safeguard our cyberspace with an anticipation of possible attacks. This paper focuses on the various vulnerabilities existing in India's nuclear assets within the cyber realm. It examines whether India's nuclear forces, particularly its C&C structures are sufficiently protected against possible cyber-attacks.

Meaning and Scope of the Term 'Cyber Warfare'

There has been no definitive explanation of cyber warfare. According to the US Joint Chief of Staff, cyber war is an armed conflict conducted through 'cyber' means to deny the opposing force to make effective use of their cyber space systems and weapons systems. (Joint Terminology for Cyber Space Actions 2010) The *Tallinn Manual of International Law* asserts that a cyber-attack is a cyber-operation (offensive or defensive), that is expected to cause injury or death to people, and/or damage or destruction to objects.' (The Tallinn Manual of International Law 2013) These definitions emphasize that cyber warfare may constitute an intentional offensive act by an adversary to interrupt the cyberspace of the target nation with the intention to achieve the desired political and military objectives. Additionally, there also exist differences among the experts on what the term 'cyber' actually means, which in turn has an impact on the perception, nature and scope of the challenge posed by the cyber threat. The word cyber here focuses on four main areas as explained in the following Table-1.

Figure-1: The Four Main Areas of Cyber

Mechanical Domain	It includes all physical infrastructure and hardware such as wires, computers, communication notes, etc.
Logical Domain	It consists of commands, which tell the hardware what to do and the software that allows transmission, creation and circulation of information.
Information and Data Domain	It incorporates all data that the system collects or stores.
Cognitive Domain	It includes human beings and their interaction with the hardware, software and information

Source: Andrew Futter, "Cyber' semantics: why we should retire the latest buzzword in security studies", *Journal of Cyber Policy*, 3:1, 2018, p. 205.

This means that any kind of cyber challenge may consist of attacks on any of the above four domains. Cyber warfare consists of cyber-attacks and cyber

exploitation. The primary goal of cyber warfare is destruction of websites and generating false information, (Schreier 2015) while cyber-attacks aim for unauthorized access to computers, computer systems or networks to gain information. (Roscini 2014, 134) Evidently, cyber-attacks on nuclear weapon systems can become a stark reality, which the states may ignore only at their own peril. Cyber attacks may not only retard nuclear facility operations, but also compromise critical components within the C&C structures.

Cyberspace suffers from inherent vulnerabilities because of the existence of innumerable entry points into the internet. (Saraswat 2018) With the development of increasingly vulnerable technologies, hackers are regularly seeking unauthorized access to closely guarded information and storming sensitive databases. There are various methods by which cyber warfare can be carried out like denial of service attack, (DoS) malware software attacks, etc as explained in the following Figure-1.

These attacks are enabled when a computer system is exposed to the rest of the world or the inherent flaws within the system are exploited. The problem is that increasing the complexity of the system may not result into protection from cyber war. The more complex the codes are, the more increased possibility of hiding errors.

Such kinds of cyber-attacks may help the adversary to control the information or to influence the information, which may help it in achieving strategic objectives during war. Here, control of information means gaining access of the information about the other party or denying the opponent from accessing its

own information. Influencing the information means providing false information that could cause the radar system to register false positives at times; displaying images/information that actually do not exist. In such situations, the adversary may not be able to detect the invasion of the opponent thus leaving it exposed to a vulnerable position.

A critical issue is that the impact of the cyber war will be temporary. The computer systems, which will be affected by it can be recovered intact at a later stage. However, the after effects of the cyber war will be manifold, especially when they are combined with the kinetic war that the cyber war causes. In the latter case, it could have a devastating impact upon the nuclear weapons capabilities of the opponent state.

The methods mentioned in Figure-1 can prove to be attractive means to rampage nuclear facilities all over the world. The first cyber-attack involving strategic assets took place in October 1979 when the North American Aerospace Defense Command (NORAD) indicated that a missile was launched from a submarine in the waters off the West Coast. (Board 1980, 1183) In recent times, there have been serious incidents of cyber attacks on nuclear and related systems. For example, British researchers discovered in 2012 that Chinese manufactured computer chips used in military weapon systems, nuclear plants, etc, all over the world contain a secret 'backdoor' that could facilitate disabling or reprogramming the chip remotely. (Curtis 2012) In a series of digital attacks between 2009-2010, the *Stuxnet* computer worm that probably arrived at Iran's nuclear plant *Natanz* on an infected USB stick attacked and infiltrated over fifteen Iranian facilities within Iran's *Natanz* nuclear power plant.* Reportedly, the recent hacking into the defence networks and intelligence agencies at the Pentagon by hackers, largely from Russia and China has increased the US concern. (Deen 2015) The most notable case of cyber-nuclear espionage was seen by Israel. In 2006, the Israeli *Mossad* planted a Trojan in the computer of the Syrian government which revealed the nature and extent of their nuclear weapons program. Later, this resulted in *Operation Orchard*, (Follarth and Stark 2009) whereby Israel attacked and destroyed the Syrian nuclear facilities. It has also raised the bar for possible cyber attacks by the Islamic State (IS) that has showed penchant for cyber technology for disseminating their influence on social media.

As opined by the IAEA chief, Amano "reports of actual or attempted cyber-attacks are now virtually a daily occurrence." India is aware of the increasing cyber threats to its critical infrastructure including its nuclear facilities. According to a report prepared in April-June 2018 by the Indian Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT-In), 35 percent of the cyber-attacks that the Indian

cyberspace witnessed came from China (Manral 2018) followed by US (17%), Russia (15%), Pakistan (9%), Canada (7%) and Germany (5%) (China was responsible for over a third of the cyber attacks on many official Indian sites, NSCS informed -2018).

India has hence embarked on a vigorous policy to strengthen its nuclear security systems including its cyber security systems. (Indian National Progress Report 2016) On June 19, 2018, the Department of Defence held a workshop on the development of the Cyber Security Framework. At the inauguration, the Defence Minister, Mrs Nirmala Sitharaman acknowledged that the Defence sector is more prone to cyber threats and hence it becomes important to safeguard our cyberspace with anticipation of possible attacks. (Workshop on cyber security framework 2018) Any incapacitation of critical information databases and/or cyber security within India's Defence sector would pose a serious threat, devastating consequences and compromise India's national security. The Defence Ministry seeks to develop a plan to implement a policy to safeguard the country's cyberspace. A Task Force involving experts from *Industry, Academia, DRDO, and Government* has been set up to chalk out a strategic roadmap for Defence in the area of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics in 2018 (Draft Defence Production Policy 2018). The aim is to provide support to invigorate cyber security infrastructure for the defence sector.

The Possibility of Cyber Attacks on India's Nuclear Assets

Understandably, India has always upheld high secrecy regarding its nuclear weapons and their related C&C structure.** India's nuclear C&C comprises of the scientific establishment, military establishment, and the political authorities and they operate in close coordination with each other.

The uppermost echelons of India's nuclear command and control structure consists of the National Command Authority (NCA, which is further divided into the Political and Executive Councils. The Political Council has the right to take a decision regarding the use of nuclear weapons. The Executive Council provides the essential inputs to the Political Council, which are vital for retaliatory action and execution of the directives of the Political Council. The Strategic Forces Command (SFC) established in January 2003 aims to manage and to administer all these strategic forces. The Political Council could directly contact the SFC in case of a prompt retaliatory action. (The Cabinet Committee on Security Reviews pre-rationalization of India's Nuclear Doctrine 2003).

The Department of Atomic Energy (DAE) and DRDO keep India's nuclear warheads in a de-mated posture. The DAE is accountable to the Prime Minister and the DRDO functions directly under the Defense Minister. (Kanwal 2006)

India's elaborate C&C structures demand a high-level coordination between the DRDO, DAE and the military, both in peace as well as at crisis times. Within the military, there is a close coordination among the Chairman Chief of Staff Committee (COSC), Chief of Integrated Defense Staff (CIDS) and the Commander-in-Chief Strategic Force Command (C-in-C SFC). It is anticipated that this multifaceted nuclear C2 of India has made or is making the nuclear weapons more secure.

India's Nuclear Retaliation

The general procedure to be followed in case of retaliation with nuclear weapons is not available in the public domain. The following interpretations have been drawn from various interviews with army officers, ex-DRDO officials and many other research published in this area. The procedure to be followed is as under:

- The chain of nuclear C&C will flow from NCA to DAE, DRDO and finally to SFC to launch control centres.
- The launch orders are given jointly by two people in India – the Prime Minister and the SFC Commander. (Interview Conducted on 16th May 2018).
- As soon as a first strike is carried out on India, the warning order will be passed to the nuclear forces by the NCP. Simultaneously, efforts will be taken to obtain information regarding the strike and the damage caused by the early information net system.
- This will be followed by the meeting between the PM, Foreign Minister, and the Chairman of the CSOC, in which the decision to retaliate will be weighed upon.
- Once the decision to retaliate has been taken, the PM will send the authentication codes to the nuclear forces.*** The electronic codes received from the PM will be matched by the codes of the SFC, the intermediate control, and LCCs to confirm its authenticity. (Interview Conducted on 16th May 2018).
- Based on the directions received from the COSC through the NCP, the SFC will pass orders for the engagement of targets at LCCs and the Air Force Wings where aircraft for aerial delivery is located. The intermediate control centres will listen in. The orders will be communicated to the Naval Station for the induction of SSBNs.
- A few minutes before the launch, the NCA will forward the codes for unlocking the Permissive Action Links (PALs) in the warheads, which will be communicated to the units concerned. (*Phawa 2008, 95*).

- At LCCs, the codes received by NCA will be matched with the already existing codes. If they match, the order will be considered as authentic. PAL codes for unlocking weapons will be fed into the weapons when received. The drill for launching the weapons will be carried out by two members of the crew in each LCC.
- In case of aircraft delivering the weapons, the authentication codes will be passed to the concerned wing. The warheads will be unlocked and then loaded into the aircraft. The aircraft may remain on the ground or get airborne and move to an RV and await further instructions from the NCP.
- Communications to the SSBN will be dependent on Very Low Frequency (VLF) and Extremely Low Frequency (ELF) and would be routed through navy. Having a PAL system will be difficult for SSBNs because of the long time involved to transmit codes on VLF and ELF. (Phawa 2008, 96).
- Thereafter, the final launch of the nuclear weapons will be conducted.

Noteworthy, India adheres to a NFU policy whereby it will retaliate only after a nuclear, biological or chemical attack has been launched by the enemy. India has reiterated that it will not be the first to carry out a nuclear weapons attack on any of its adversaries. (The Cabinet Committee on Security Reviews pre-rationalization of India's Nuclear Doctrine 2003)¹

Two things are of utmost importance:

1. India requires to be able to assess the degree of danger inflicted by the first strike of the opponent. It is vital for NCA to have information vis-à-vis the numbers, characteristics and deployment of enemy's nuclear weapons, its C&C structure etc. After this, it is crucial to have information about the total weapons, which have survived the first strike. These factors will decide India's retaliatory action.
2. It is assumed that India should be able to retaliate within a particular time frame. Firstly, such a time frame will thwart the chances of accidental or inadvertent use of nuclear weapons. Secondly, soon after the first attacks, there will be international pressure on India not to carry out nuclear strikes on the adversary. Thirdly, a longer time for retaliation raises another fear that an enemy could launch a second attack destroying all the retaliatory capability of India. (Phawa 2008, 101).

These two points prove without a doubt that India needs to have a high level of secure and quick C2 systems to enable successful retaliation. Any

disruption within the C&C system resulting from cyber warfare agents will increase the reaction time of India's retaliation and impede India's military operations. There can be an uncontrolled impact of such cyber warfare and can potentially result in catastrophic attacks upon the critical infrastructure and pose major risks for radioactive and nuclear materials in the nuclear field. It is important to note that such degree of cyber warfare are mostly politically motivated and targeted to cripple a nation.

India's Position on Cyber Warfare against Nuclear Weapons

India has maintained that there are no gaps or any possibility left for having a cyber-warfare against the nuclear assets of India. The reasons given are as follows:

1. The electronic control systems and plant control systems are designed and developed in-house using custom build hardware and software subjected to regular verification and validation.
2. The critical infrastructure of India is isolated from the internet.
3. There is a system of quarterly cyber security audit of DAE, and they submit all their reports to Computer and Information Security Advisory Group (CISAG) of DAE.
4. The DAE also involves Standardisation Testing and Quality Certification (STQC) of Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology to test those systems, which are connected to the internet and where there could be any possibilities of vulnerabilities.
5. The DAE also took part in drills conducted by the Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) of India to prepare for and to actually face cyber-attacks. (Government of India 2017).
6. Similarly, India has designed safe and reliable designs, that have control and protection features to detect any deviation in plant safety parameters. It has several safety features like even the automatic shutdown of the reactor.
7. Even if, any radioactivity is released, there are arrangements by Emergency Preparedness and Response Emergency Preparedness and Response to protect the people from the harmful radiations. (Government of India 2017).

Despite the vigorous safeguards against potential cyber intrusions, it is undeniable that India is heavily dependent on computer systems and to some extent, the internet in all sectors including defence. Arguably, one cannot stop viruses from entering into cyberspace. The moment one virus is removed, hackers

are already working on it to introduce a different type of virus. So cyber “warfare is a continuum.... it will never stop.” (Bagla 2018) Most equipment and technology for setting up cyber security infrastructure in India are currently procured from global sources. These systems are vulnerable to cyber threats just like any other connected system. Besides, many engineered systems of nuclear weapons are still dependent on digital computational parts that can be hacked easily. Any cyber-attack on such digital infrastructure, which is critical in nature, poses a serious risks to the coordination of the various agencies within the nuclear establishment. It may trigger a false or no information alarm and lead to non-working of the nuclear weapons system. According to Tariq Rauf, director of the Disarmament, Arms Control and Non-Proliferation Programme at the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, (SIPRI) nuclear power plants and the nuclear industry rely intensively on computer systems and computer codes. (Deen 2015) One can assume, that given India’s dependency on digital technology, it may rely on computer systems and computer codes not only for its nuclear power plants but also for the launching and security of its nuclear weapons. Hence, any targeted attacks through any malware could have catastrophic consequences for both our nuclear safety and security.

While the wave of digital technology has brought in revolutionary changes towards development, it has also resulted in the surge of sophisticated hackers who are being trained to be cyber warriors for various offensive cyber activities like hacking, espionage and intrusion. These hackers sometimes act as lone wolves or are trained by rogue nations to develop innovative methods for launching cyber-attacks on critical infrastructure systems. They attack hardware or firmware, which affects the *root of trust*. Since the security of software is more difficult, hackers find it easier to exploit the lower stack in the technological infrastructure like the physical aspects of computer systems and its components. This way, cyber warriors are able to compromise a system and undermine the core *trust* of the device.

Possible Vulnerabilities of India’s Nuclear Arsenal to Cyber Warfare

A. Systems designed by India to assess the damage of first strike and vehicle transportation systems:

There have been systems in India to read the degree of radiations emitted during a nuclear and radiological emergency. According to the Government of India, there are five main circumstances in which it is assumed that nuclear emergency has been declared:

- An accident taking place in any nuclear facility of the nuclear fuel cycle including the nuclear reactor, or in a facility using radioactive sources.

- A 'criticality' accident in a nuclear fuel cycle.
- An accident during the transportation of radioactive material.
- The malicious use of radioactive material by terrorists for dispersing radioactive material in the environment.
- A large-scale nuclear disaster resulting from a nuclear weapon attack. [(as had happened at Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan) (Management of Nuclear and Radiological Emergency)]

Therefore, to respond to any crisis, it is first essential to know that the crisis has actually occurred. For this, India has designed a National Disaster Monitoring System which is dependent upon computers to provide relevant information. The Bhabha Atomic Research Centre BARC has established 24 radiation monitoring centres across the country to provide online information regarding radiation levels at various locations in the country. (ensuring Safety of Professionals) This information is dependent on computers that can be hacked or jammed by the enemy. Under such conditions, it will be difficult for India to access any information. Cyber war against these systems will result in increased time for India to retaliate and impede communication with the DAE. (as it is believed that nuclear attack might disturb other communication means such as telecommunications as well).

The problem becomes more acute when these technologies are used to track the vehicle, which is carrying such radiological materials. Radiological materials are transported during the time of crises, as they need to be assembled for firing a nuclear warhead. For this, GPS systems have been mounted on the vehicles carrying these sensitive materials. (Electronic Tracking for the transport of nuclear and other material) The problem is that GPS systems can be 'spoofed' carrying a satellite causing it to read a faulty data. This may further create problems for India to carry out 'retaliation'. Further, the AERB has mentioned about the existence of the electronic systems to ensure the safe transfer of nuclear material. (Security of Radioactive Sources in Radiation Facilities) Typically, an electronic tracking device is fixed to the vehicle carrying the nuclear material. Electronic tracking uses GPS, satellite communication or cellular general packet radio services. (GPRS) These three systems work together to know the transit of the vehicle. Any disturbance, jamming or faulty information may lead to a 'sabotage' of the radiological items.

B. Pal systems of India

In India, there are 'codes' which are needed to unlock the nuclear weapon system and to mount it on the warhead. However, no open source has mentioned the form of these codes i.e., electronic/non-electronic. The officers working on

the issue have mentioned in questionnaires that these codes are no doubt electronic, something similar to the PAL system of the US.

PAL was designed to prevent the unauthorized use of nuclear weapons. Some of these systems can disable and destroy the nuclear weapons in case of some incidents of tempering. Now, the concern has been mentioned that these systems can be prone to cyber-attacks. PAL codes are entered to arm the weapons and the messages are sent in digital format via the secure Automatic Digital Network and then relayed to aircraft via single-sideband radio transmitters to High-Frequency Global Communications System. It is feared that the PAL systems are prone to cyber-attacks. The questionnaire responded by the anonymous (See Annexure 1) mentioned that India do have a digital code systems on the line of the US. Even, when the nuclear warheads are loaded on the missiles, the codes are used. Under such conditions, the possibility of cyber threats against these codes cannot be ignored.

C. India's nuclear weapons: No longer de-mated

The argument that India's nuclear warheads are in a de-mated status and are not prone to cyber threats is not entirely true. The Kargil Conflict 1999 and the 2001 Parliament attacks made India realize that it needs new institutional procedures for operational readiness. (Kampani 2015, 386) During the *Kargil war*, the civil bureaucracy assumed that India could retaliate within 72 hours. However, the time taken to assemble nuclear weapon was around one week. The 2001-02 crisis also shows an actual gap between the plans and papers concerning operational readiness and the actual possibility of a launch of nuclear weapons. As a result, new protocols have been ensured to address this gap, which states that

1. The first state of nuclear force alteration begins simultaneously with only conventional mobilization.
2. The second stage involves mating of a nuclear warhead with the trigger.
3. The final stage involves the firing of the nuclear weapons. (Kampani 2015, 386).

Further, new missiles like Agni V have the canister system, meaning that India is not entirely following the de-mated system of the nuclear missiles. (India test fires Agni 5 Ballistic Missiles, the trial successful 2018) This factor alone raises the threshold of the cyber-attacks on the nuclear weapons.

D. Hacking of SSBNs system

India's adversaries may have the technique to hack the much-talked about, Arihant missile, which has given India a much-needed nuclear submarine

capability. Nuclear submarines are considered as a vital part of nuclear deterrence because they can stay hidden underwater for a considerable amount of time. Nuclear submarines generally depend on the ELF or VLF radio waves for communications because only very low or extremely low frequencies can penetrate the water at those depths. (Singh and Pal 2003) The adversary may have the potential to hack the transmitters carrying these radio waves. (Futter 2018, 144) This can probably have an impact on the second retaliatory capability and the operations to be carried out by nuclear submarines.

E. Use of space and satellites in nuclear weapons launch

The realm of outer space has increasingly become a part of the nuclear C&C system. (Lele 2011, 290), India is working on the development of the fourth generation GSAT to connect all the three domains that are sea-based assets, (warships, nuclear submarines, and aircraft carriers) land-based assets, (troops formation, conventional war technology, ballistic and cruise missiles) and air force assets. (combat aircraft) (Ehtisham 2018) These kinds of communication satellites help the armed forces to carry out communication between different parts of the C&C structure, which is vital during a nuclear weapons launch.

India is dependent on 13 satellites to carry out remote sensing activities. (Singh 2017) These 13 satellites include the recently launched Cartosat-1, Carosat-2 and RISAT-1 and RISAT-2 satellites. These satellites can be used to detect images during the night. (Cartosat-1: 10 years completion in Orbit from 2005–2015) India has the SAR system, which gives data about weather conditions, terrain features, exact locations of the targets, and information like whether such targets are surrounded by civilian population, and if so, what is the total number of the concentration of civilian population. SAR can help to differentiate between terrain features and actual targets. (Lele 2012) This shows India's dependency on various satellites to carry out and/or perform essential functions in nuclear C&C systems.

India uses satellite, as well as telemetry data during missile flight. According to Rajaram Nagappa, telemetry is a method of onboard measurement of data and its transmission to the ground stations. There are various parameters like pressure, temperature, strain, electric current and voltage, which are monitored onboard and then these are transmitted. This can even include information about the health of the vehicle. It has been mentioned that DRDO makes the onboard computers and these are hence, highly unlikely to be hacked. Further, they run on the *Linux system* rather than *Windows*, which makes them even more secure against cyber threats. However, the possibility of the satellites being hacked

cannot be ignored. Telemetry is also used to analyze whether the missile has followed the designed path and whether it has attained the desired height of burst. Till now, India has used telemetry data for carrying out missile tests. (Kampani 1998) There are incidents in the past where the military satellites were hacked in the US. (Kumar 2018) If the adversary processes the same in India, it could pose several problems ranging from early warning, to detection of targets from the earth and disturbance of the communication systems. This would adversely interfere with the launch of nuclear weapons.

F. Terrorist cyber-attacks on civilian nuclear reactors

The threat of cyber-attacks by terrorist groups is far greater than that compared to cyber attacks by states. The reason is that it requires very little investment and little computer knowledge, which is available easily. In India, such threats are addressed by CISAG that is responsible for conducting audits of information systems, framing guidelines and plans for mitigating cyber-attacks and its effects. (Kazi and Nayan 2016, 28) The use of a USB or external driver is forbidden to secure vital computer systems. In addition, there is limited internet connectivity in the area. However, new hacking techniques have made cyber warfare against these systems, a possibility. (Rajagopalan 2016).

The DAE mentioned that AERB has prescribed necessary codes, guides and other regulatory documents to ensure safety of nuclear weapons. They also have their own licensing systems to ensure safety of nuclear plants. The AERB also conducts regular inspections to monitor compliance with the established regulatory requirements. (Lok Sabha Starred Question No51 2016).

The civilian nuclear facilities of India consist of a large number of computers distributed across the plants. These computers are responsible for performing various functions like protection of the reactor safety, control functions from information collected from displays, etc. If information on these computer systems is hacked by malicious elements, it could lead to severe accidental conditions. (Babu 2013).

There are two main systems for security in any nuclear facility: Instrument and Control Security (ICS) and Facility Network Security (FNS). The ICS ensures safety and controls systems such as the reactor protection system, reactor trip system and power regulation system. The FNS, on the other hand, secures the monitoring network, which has the administrative, and management functions. If there is a cyber-war against these systems, FNS will lead to transmission of data that may be lost or transmitted to external persons. Alternatively, ICS failure could lead to a series of situations including the release of radioactivity. Any modification in the software of ICS will result in problems related to safety.

The safety mechanisms will not be executed at the required rate or in the required response time. (Babu 2013).

The DAE states that in case of any such events, there will be an automatic shutdown of the reactor thus minimizing the chances of spreading radiological emissions. However, their dependence on the computers cannot be ignored. Any delay in the computer system resulting from the cyber-attacks may prevent the shutdown of the system.

G False information through social media to create disturbance

In present times, social media, especially *twitter* has emerged as an important platform for transfer of personal information to the world at large. These accounts are largely not very well protected and it is relatively easy to hack an account and to pass on wrong information, which may create panic and disturbance at large. In short, the risk of 'spoofing' is always present in such systems. For example, In July 2014, the Israeli military *twitter* account handle was hacked and a report was published that a top secret nuclear facility at Dimona had been attacked by rockets which had caused a radiation catastrophe. (Tadeo 2014) Spreading such false information may be more attractive to terrorists.

Emerging Cyber War Threat without the Internet, WiFi or Router

It is a misconception that cyber-attacks cannot happen if a computer is not connected to internet, intranet, WiFi or router. The incident of *Stuxnet* virus on Iranian enrichment facilities have clearly shown that cyber-attacks can be carried out even without the internet. (Zetter 2014) There are six main ways, as mentioned below, through which air-gripped systems can be exploited:

1. Via an 'insider' threat which is perhaps the most important and perhaps the easiest method. Such insider threats can be deliberate or unintentional. (Due to ignorance of the employee or negligence).
2. Through remote maintenance and dial-in ports, i.e. by hacking.
3. By developing and accessing built-in backdoors, remotely. (These may have been developed when the system was manufactured.)
4. By jumping the air gap via other electromagnetic tools.
5. By wiretapping.
6. By intercepting radar and other insecure communications.
7. Exposing the computer systems during upgradation of some software or during the maintenance of the system. (Futter 2018, 102).

Karl Grindal explains an episode of the attack on the US air gripped systems:

In the summer of 2008, an infected thumb drive, possibly dropped in a parking lot or slipped into briefcase, was inserted into a US military laptop on a base in the Middle East. The technically advanced virus stored on the USB stick penetrated the air gap that separates the military's secure networks from the internet at large, infecting both classified and unclassified networks. Once beyond the gap, the malware rapidly replicated throughout the network by inflicting additional thumb drives, leading personnel to unintentionally spread the virus further. (Futter 2018, 65).

Evidently, India's nuclear weapons do face cyber vulnerabilities. In 2016, it was found that Chinese hackers breached sensitive computer systems at the headquarters of the Eastern Naval Command in Visakhapatnam, where the indigenous nuclear submarine, '*Arihant*' has been undergoing sea trials. (Vasudeva 2012) Reportedly, the computer systems of DRDO were breached and some sensitive files were leaked. (Jain 2015) A top defense ministry officer admitted that 'cyber command would ensure both offensive and defensive cyber security capabilities. Issues like cyber warfare, cyber terrorism, and cyber espionage would be taken care of by cyber command.' (Sagar 2014) Given, the vast advancement in cyber technology, India's nuclear weapons remain vulnerable to the following possible cyber-attacks scenarios in future that can damage its critical infrastructure.

- Adversaries may try to hack the nuclear weapons' system of India with an intention to damage it.
- By using cyber warfare capabilities, the adversaries may try to know the exact locations of the weapon system in order to target it first, in the conflict.
- Adversaries may impact the satellite systems thus making it difficult for the nuclear command center to have on the spot communications, selection of target and adversary information.
- There may be intentional hacking of the system to cause a faulty selection of targets.
- There may be an active stealing of India's nuclear data.

Given the threat perspectives, it is of urgent necessity that India develops means to manage and safeguard against cyber threats and maintain the survival of its critical retaliatory capabilities.

Conclusion

The possibility of cyber-attacks on nuclear weapons and its related infrastructure is increasing. The computer systems used across all nuclear weapon

enterprises can potentially fail due to a variety of reasons including as a result of incorrect, incomplete or faulty design and/or manufacture of the key components, various problems with the software or the hardware, coding errors in the software being used like computer bugs and other problems arising due to human interaction with these systems such as maintenance, updating and upgrading. These risks must be considered as important factors while devising current risk management approaches in India's nuclear policies for mitigating all cyber threats. As mentioned by Yukiya Amano, the Director of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), 'the issue of cyber-attacks on nuclear-related facilities or activities should be taken very seriously. We will never know in certainty if we know everything or if it is just the tip of the iceberg. This is not an imaginary risk.' The intensity of episodes with cyber-attacks on nuclear systems has increased after the STUNEX virus attacks. Recently, in 2014, there have been malware attacks on Japan's Nuclear Power Plant, cyber-attacks on German nuclear systems in April 2016 and hacking of the computer systems of a South Korean nuclear plant in February 2017. (McCurry 2014) India cannot declare itself as an exceptional case, which is foolproof to cyber threats. It is time to recognize the threat and to have a suitable policy to deal with it.

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- * Once inside the computer system, Stuxnet searched for software that controls machines called centrifuges. Once it inserted itself into it, it seized control of the centrifuges and alternatively made the centrifuges spin dangerously fast, for about 15 minutes, before returning to normal speed. Then, about a month later, it slowed the centrifuges down for around 50 minutes. This was repeated for several months. The excessive speeds caused, infected machines to disintegrate. Reportedly, Iran decommissioned around 20 per cent of its centrifuges in the Natanz plant during the attack. See "Timeline: How Stuxnet attacked a nuclear plant," BBC, 2018, URL: <https://www.bbc.com/timelines/zc6fbk7#z32pycw>, accessed 25 August 2018.
 - ** There has been no official statement yet on the number of nuclear arsenals or detailed version of the command and control structure. The government to date has provided only the institutional framework. For details, see Ramana MV (2009), "India Nuclear Enclave and the Practice of Secrecy", 2009, URL: <https://www.princeton.edu/~ramana/India-Nuclear-Enclave-And-Practice-Of-Secrecy.pdf>, accessed 18 April 2018.
 - *** The COSC will translate the selected option into a specific direction for the engagement of targets and pass it to NCP so that the same can be forwarded to the SFC, the intermediate control centres (formation and unit headquarters) and the Launch Control Centres (LCCs).
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